

Multi-Objective Mechanical Optimisation of Lattice Cores

Athina Kontopoulou*, Bing Zhang*, Fabrizio Scarpa*, Giuliano Allegri*

*Bristol Composites Institute, University of Bristol.

Structural weight can be reduced by substituting conventional monolithic components with sandwich ones. Our work aims to **optimise** the mechanical properties of lattice cores, which can be manufactured through conventional 3D printing techniques. The topology of the lattice unit cell is crucial for the ensuing mechanical performance. Here, we aim to **maximise the specific compressive (E_2) and out-of-plane shear stiffness (G_{23})** of lattice cores using a **multi-objective genetic algorithm (GA)**. A Representative Volume Element (RVE) for parametric lattice designs is used in a finite element (FE) modelling framework, which is incorporated within a GA-driven optimisation loop. **Manufacturing constraints** are accounted for in the optimisation. A **relative density constraint** for the lattice design is also considered.

Conclusions

Tapering the struts has a beneficial effect on both compressive and out-of-plane shear stiffnesses, which can be increased up to 11% and 5%, respectively. The optimum tapering ratio $\beta \sim 0.7$ is independent of the YRVE and relative density, with an optimum α factor at ~ 0.82 .

Future work

Investigate the dynamic properties of the optimum lattice structures through numerical predictions and experimental validation with vibration transmissibility tests.